

Old Gods and the New: (Re)Invention of Athenian Cults in the Hellenistic Period

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Abstract

The history of Athens in the Hellenistic period is a turbulent one. The polis was reduced to a second- or even a third-rate power and had to deal with powerful neighboring empires. Political and economic tides affected Athenian religion and its cult practices. Depending on the current political context and their material wealth, Athenians used their religion to establish their place in a wider Hellenistic world, to promote their polis, or as a means of foreign policy either by honoring or placating kings and other mighty men and women. This paper aims to give an overview of the development of cults and cult practices in Athens roughly from the death of Alexander the Great to the Sulla's sacking of the city in 86 BC. The focus will be on the establishment of new cults and the resurgence of old ones in a new context.

Introduction

The turbulent history of the Athenian state in the Hellenistic period can be divided into roughly two parts. The first one would coincide with the majority of the third century BCE. It is characterized by a tight Macedonian grip, war, destruction, economic downfall and long-term decline. That ended in 229 BC and the next thirty years were a sort of interregnum. During that

period, Athens, supported by mighty Ptolemaic kings in Egypt, held a strongly neutral course in their foreign policy.

The proximity of Macedonia once again proved to be a problem for Athens. Hostilities broke out in 201/200 BC. This time, however, Athens was allied with the Attalids from Pergamum, Rhodes and most importantly, Rome. Since the very beginning of the 2nd century BC, Athens was a staunch ally of Rome throughout the Second Macedonian War (200–197 BC), the Syrian War (192–188 BC) and the Third Macedonian War (171–167 BC). The only exception was the First Mithridatic War (88–84 BC) where Athens was an ally of the Pontic king, which ended in disaster.

The alliance with Rome, apart from military security, had its economic benefits. After the war with Perseus, Romans gave Athens the city of Haliartos in Boiotia, and the islands of Lemnos, Imbros, Skyros and most importantly, Delos. The Romans abolished custom duties on Delos and soon enough the island became a trading hub in the Aegean, especially after the destruction of Corinth (146 BC) and the establishment of Roman province of Asia (129 BC). The acquisition of the island resulted in the increased economic wealth of Athens itself.

All these things influenced the Athenian religion and cults. The internationalization of Delos and Athens, especially its port of Piraeus, syncretistic tendencies in religion inside the Hellenistic frame, powerful and influential individuals – all this had a visible effect on Attic religious practice. On the other hand, Athenians themselves tried to resurrect old traditions and festivals.¹

¹ To this very day the best overview of Athenian history in Hellenistic period remains Christian Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, trans. Deborah L. Schneider (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1997); for the Athenian cults in classical period see: Susan Deacy, “Famous Athens, Divine Polis: The Religious System at Athens,” in *A Companion to Greek Religion*, ed. Daniel Ogden, 221–235 (Malden MA: Blackwell Publishing, 2007); while Emily Kearns, “The Heroes of Attica,” *Bulletin Supplement* 57, (London: Institute of Classical Studies, University of London, 1989): 139–237 contains the catalogue of Attic heroes.

Domestic cults

The Hellenistic period was a time of intensive permeation of various cults in the Mediterranean and Athens was no exception. The 3rd and 2nd centuries BC are, on the one hand, characterized by the worship of old gods and the activities of old cults, but on the other hand, new gods and new cults were introduced. Still, this dichotomy was not that sharp, since old gods could obtain new garb and new ones are often associated with their older counterparts. Athenian religious life cannot and should not be separated from festivals that have accompanied it. These festivals contained various contests, mostly athletic but also theatrical and poetic. The organization of these festivals, and especially their funding, was left to wealthy Athenians. This was a way for them to show off their wealth and to gain status and prestige in the community. The inscriptions about these *agonothetes* are clear evidence of what was expected of them, how much money they spent and what honors they could hope for.²

There are two periods in the history of Athenian cults in Hellenistic times. The first coincides roughly with the 3rd century BC when Athens was experiencing military defeats and economic difficulties. There are relatively few pieces of evidence of cult celebrations from that time. It seems that there were interruptions in the celebration of some festivals, such as the *Panathenaia* and the Eleusinian mysteries. The celebrations were relatively modest. The second period lasted until Sulla's conquest of Athens in March 86 BC. During that time Athens enjoyed a period of peace, stability and economic progress. Some new cults were introduced, and the old ones were celebrated with greater pomp.

The most important Athenian festival was the Panathenaic ceremony. Cult practices associated with the *Panathenaia* were followed by gymnastic, musical and equestrian

² On *agonothetai* see inscriptions: *Syll.*³ 667; *IG* II³ 1 991, 995, 1034, 1160; *IG* II³ 1 1022 honors the *athlothetai* who organized the Panathenaics received; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 169.

competitions.³ At the beginning of the 3rd century BC, there were interruptions in the celebration of this festival, but the Athenians nevertheless strove to organize them regularly. There are inscriptions that testify that they were sending special envoys (*theoroi*) to invite other cities to participate. The list of winners proves that many foreigners came to compete at that festival, especially in the 2nd century BC. Besides, many Hellenistic rulers took part in the competition, although not personally, but rather through their subjects.⁴ The Athenians also used these special occasions to thank their deserving citizens and *euergetes* in a festive circumstance.⁵ The *Panathenaia* were celebrated even after Sulla.⁶

The Eleusinian mysteries were of great importance and renown. Because the Macedonians held Eleusis in the first half of the 3rd century BC, the mysteries were seldom celebrated. After the a war (268–262/1 BC), they were celebrated continuously. The honors – a myrtle crown, public praise and an inscribed stele – that the Athenians bestowed upon the organizers of the mysteries testify to their value.⁷ The Eleusinian mysteries were very popular in the Hellenistic world. Their eschatological character and openness for all were very receptive to the Hellenistic man. The Athenians invited foreigners, among them the Hellenistic kings, to come and be initiated into the mysteries. Prominent Romans too wished to be initiated. The Athenians granted this wish to Lucius

³ Events on the *Panathenaia*: *IG II³ 1 1022*, ll. 9–10; girls who wove the *peplos* for goddess Athena: *IG II² 1942*, 1034+1943, 3448; *IG II³ 1 1284*; *SEG 13:143*; the festivities lasted 23–30. *hekatombaion*, see John D. Mikalson, *The Sacred and Civil Calendar of Athenian Year*, (Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1975): 34; John D. Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1998), 237.

⁴ *IG II³ 1 1145*, 1239; *IG II² 2313*, 2314, 2316, 2317; Polyb. 28.19; George R. Edwards, “Panathenaics of Hellenistic and Roman Times,” *Hesperia* 26/4 (1957): 330; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 169, 225, 238–240; Aleksandar Simić, “Athens in the Hellenistic period: From Antigonos Gonatas until Sulla (262/1–86 BC)” (master’s thesis, University of Belgrade, 2018), 99.

⁵ *IG II³ 1 1313*, l. 40; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 240.

⁶ *IG II² 1043*, ed. 54; Edwards, “Panathenaics of Hellenistic and Roman Times,” 322–323.

⁷ *IG II³ 1 915*, 1164, 1188; Mikalson, *The Sacred and Civil Calendar of Athenian Year*, 65; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 169.

Cornelius Sulla (for the same political and safety reasons as Demetrius Poliorcetes earlier), Quintus Tullius Cicero, but rejected Marcus Licinius Crassus.⁸

From 273/2 BC the cult of *Athena Soteira* (the Savior) appears. She was always paired with *Zeus Soter*. The inscriptions testify that the priesthood of *Athena Soteira* regularly offered sacrifices and organized the festival of *Diisoteria*.⁹ Some sixty years later (215/14 BC), Athenians revived yet another festival called *Aianteia*, dedicated to the hero Ajax. One of the competitions during the festival was a maritime race of the *epeboi* near the Salamis, the birthplace of the hero.¹⁰ The Goddess Artemis was much revered in Athens, where she was praised with the attribute of *Kalliste* (The Most Beautiful). Since the second century (approx. 170 BC) a new attribute of Artemis emerges on the prytanic inscriptions, that of *Phosphoros* (The Lightbringer). Stephanie Lynn Budin thinks that this attribute of Artemis is somehow connected to Hekate, because both goddesses are iconographically connected to torch-bearing.¹¹

The Athenians freed themselves from Macedonian rule in 229 BC. To commemorate this event, two leading Athenians at that time, the brothers Eurykleides and Mikion from the deme of

⁸ Plut. *Demetr.* 26, *Sull.* 16; Cic. *De Or.* III 20, 75; the official guests of the mysteries were the citizens of Miletus: *IG II³ 1 1372*, and Gonnoi: *IG II³ 1 1145*, B. *IG II³ 1 1387*; Polybius mentions (18.19) that the Athenians had sent envoys in Egypt in 168 BC to summon the royal family to participate in the mysteries; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 221, 294; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 238; Karen L. Edwards, "Captive Gods: Romans and Athenian Religion from 229 B.C. to the Age of Augustus" (PhD diss., University of Virginia, 1997), 71–73, 101; Antonia Tripolitis, *Religions of the Hellenistic-Roman Age* (Grand Falls, MI: William B. Eerdmans, 2002), 21.

⁹ *IG II³ 1 902*, 903, 905, 953; Priests and Priestesses, 20; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 103.

¹⁰ Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 168; Edwards, "Captive Gods" 61.

¹¹ The priests of *Kalliste*: *IG II³ 1 1028*, 1339; *IG II² 4667*, 4668; *Phosphoros*: *IG II³ 1 1324*, l. 10; *IG II³ 1 1328*, l. 9; Robert Parker, *Polytheism and Society at Athens*, (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005), 400, 404; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 169; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 176; Stephanie L. Budin, *Artemis*, (London: Routledge, 2016), 65–66.

Kephysia organized the cult of *Demos* and *Kharitai*. The priesthood of that cult was a hereditary position held by their family.¹²

The material welfare of the 2nd century BC marked a new period for the Athenian religious and cult life. Athens regained control over the island of Skyros, the legendary resting place of the hero Theseus, in 166 BC. The Athenians used this occasion to revive the festival of *Theseia* in honor of one of their founding heroes. The first recorded celebration was in 161 BC and *agonothetes* (the person responsible for organization) was Nikogenes. *Theseia*, unlike some other festivals, was restricted only to Athenians, except for foreign mercenaries in Athenian employment. The *Theseia* was also an important ephebic festival, where they could show their skills. This festival had a distinct militaristic character.¹³

Another renewed festival was that of *Thargelia*, dedicated to Apollo. There are relatively few shreds of evidence for this festival in Hellenistic times, but it can be surmised that the festival included sacrifices and gymnastic contests. All the Athenian magistrates participated in the ceremony and the slaves were freed from work on the day of the festival.¹⁴

Pythais was a significant religious festival during which many Athenian magistrates, ephebes, equestrians and other prominent citizens – between 300 and 500 of them – would carry the first harvest from Apollo's birthplace on Delos to his residence in Delphi. This procession was renewed in 138/7 BC and the subsequent ones were held in 128/7, 106/5 and 98/7 BC. The Athenians had trouble funding the last *Pythais*, and therefore the wealthy citizens gave their own money several

¹²IG II³ 1 1137, l. 39; IG II³ 1 1160, l. 24; IG II² 4676, 5029, 5047; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 180; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 160–161; Simić, “Athens in the Hellenistic period: From Antigonus Gonatas until Sulla,” 102.

¹³IG II² 956, 957–961; Mikalson, *The Sacred and Civil Calendar of Athenian Year*, 70–71; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 241; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 234; Parker, *Polytheism and Society in Athens*, 483–484; Donald G. Kyle, “Athletics in Ancient Athens,” *Mnemosyne Supplement* 95 (Leiden: Brill, 1993), 40.

¹⁴SEG 21:469; Simić, “Athens in the Hellenistic period: From Antigonus Gonatas until Sulla,” 100.

times. The procession that should have been held in 90/89 BC was cancelled and never organized again.¹⁵

The guild of dionysiac artists (*technitai*) was closely connected with the reorganization of the *Pythais*. Since the beginning of the 3rd BC, they had privileges with the Delphic Amphictyony. With the renewal of the Pythian procession, the Amphictyony renewed these privileges to the Dionysiac *technitai*. However, the Athenian guild got in conflict with a similar association from Isthmos. In the end, Romans also got involved, and they backed the Athenian organization.¹⁶

Delos was known in Hellenistic times as an international religious centre. It owed this to the fact that it was the legendary birthplace of Apollo and Artemis. It is therefore not surprising that Apollo's priest was the most influential among the priesthood of the island. When the Athenians took over the island in 166 BC, they imported the Athenian cults, and the Delian cults were Atticized. Thus, the inscriptions from the middle of the second century BC represent a sort of gradation of island cults. Apollo, of course, was the most important, but Zeus and Athena were highly respected in three forms: *Kynthios* and *Kynthia* (named after the Delian mountain of Kynthion), *Soter* and *Soteira*, and *Poliaios* and *Polias*. Artemis had a low position on the island and in the last place was the local hero Annios.¹⁷

Foreign cults - Eastern and Western

Various eastern cults existed in Athens both before and during the Hellenistic era.

¹⁵Cf. *Syll.*³ 696, 697, 711; *IG II²* 2336; Parker, *Polytheism and Society in Athens*, 83–84; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 276.; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 245; Simić, "Athens in the Hellenistic period: From Antigonos Gonatas until Sulla," 100–101.

¹⁶*Syll.*³ 399, 692, 704, 705; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 277–278; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 239–241; Simić, "Athens in the Hellenistic period: From Antigonos Gonatas until Sulla," 101.

¹⁷*ID* 2605; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 202; Edwards, "Captive Gods," 38–39.

Egyptian gods, mostly Isis and Sarapis (or Serapis), were the most popular and the most influential. Athenians knew of the god Ammon in the Classical period, and the first temple of Isis was built in Piraeus before 330 BC. Crucial for the establishment of the Egyptian gods in Athens was the political support of the first Ptolemaic kings. The Greek traveler Pausanias said that the Athenians started worshipping Sarapis under the influence of Ptolemy, but he doesn't specify which one. The coming of the god Sarapis in Athens was probably a process that lasted through the reigns of Ptolemy I through Ptolemy III since all three kings had close ties to Athens. The worshippers of Sarapis (the *Sarapiastai*) were not numerous in the beginning, but later their numbers grew since the cult was supported by the Athenian state.¹⁸

The goddess Isis had a brighter future. She was popular in the whole Hellenistic world, especially in ports and trading towns, where a lot of different people mixed. She first appeared in Athens and Delos as *Isis Pelagia* (of the Sea). She had her first temple dedicated to her in Piraeus a little before 333 BC, the very beginning of the Hellenistic age.¹⁹ Later her cult grew, and she became the most respected of all Egyptian deities. On the island of Delos existed the so-called Serapeion, a temple complex dedicated to Sarapis, but containing an important shrine dedicated to Isis. Isis, Sarapis and Anubis were worshipped as a sort of trinity on Delos²⁰

¹⁸ Paus. 1.12, 18; the priest of Ammon: *IG II²* 1282; Sterling Dow, "The Egyptian Cults in Athens," *The Harvard Theological Review* 30 no. 4 (1937): 228, 231; Julietta Steinhauer, "Cult Associations in the Post-Classical Polis," (PhD diss., University of St. Andrews, 2012), 52–54; Kelly A. Moss, "The Development and Diffusion of the Cult of Isis in the Hellenistic Period" (master's thesis, University of Arizona, 2017), 64, 85; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 166, 210.

¹⁹ Moss, "The Development and Diffusion of the Cult of Isis in the Hellenistic Period," 63, 64, 67; Tripolitis, *Religions of the Hellenistic-Roman Age*, 27.

²⁰ *ID* 1510; *IG II²* 2336, l. 47; Steinhauer, "Cult Associations in the Post-Classical Polis," 49–54; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 256; Moss, "The Development and Diffusion of the Cult of Isis in the Hellenistic Period," 75–76; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 28, 211; Elizabeth G. Huzar, "Roman-Egyptian Relations in Delos," *The Classical Journal* 57 no. 4 (1962): 173; Edwards, "Captive Gods," 49–50.

Merchants coming from the Levant brought their gods with them. The citizens of Berytos (modern-day Beirut) organized a *koinon* (association) centered on the temple of Poseidon. The citizens of Tyre organized themselves around the cult of their city god Melqart, who was identified with Herakles. Apart from them, a Jewish community attested for on the island, where they had built a synagogue. The cult of Aphrodite Ourania was brought to Piraeus by merchants from Citium on Cyprus was thriving. The first record mentioning the Carian cult of Zeus Labraundos dates from 299/8 BC. From Syria came the goddess Athargatis with her companion Hadad. They were worshipped as Aphrodite Hagne and Zeus Hadatos.²¹

The only western cult was the cult of the goddess Roma. Clear political reasons had lain behind Roma's introduction to the Athenian pantheon. Romans became the protectors of Athens and Delos, and this was a way for Athenians to show them gratitude. The Roman cult was soon linked with domestic ones: in Athens with *Demos* and *Kharitai* and on Delos with *Demos* and *Hestia*. The accompanying festival of *Romaia* was held in Athens only once and on Delos multiple times.²²

Individuals as an object of worship

The Hellenistic era brought with it the rise of many extremely powerful figures, most of them being Hellenistic kings. The relations of cities and kings were multifaceted and complex, and

²¹ Tyrians: *ID* 1519; Berytians: *ID* 1520; *IG* II² 1271; Jews: *SEG* 32:809, cf: *ID* 2328, 2330–2332; Athargatis: *ID* 2240; Steinhauer, “Cult Associations in the Post-Classical Polis,” 42; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 92–93, 213, 217; Monika Trümper, “The Oldest Original Synagogue Building in the Diaspora: The Delos Synagogue Reconsidered,” *Hesperia* 73 no. 4 (2004): 513–514.

²² *Priests and Priestesses*, 22; *IG* II² 1938, 5047; *IG* II² 2336, l. 45; *ID* 1950, 2605; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 181, 275; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 249; Edwards, “Captive Gods,” 91–92.

often they entered the cult sphere. It was not unusual for a certain poleis to bestow divine honors upon a king.

The first case in Athens was the worship of Alexander the Great himself. The assumption is that the Athenians had bestowed upon him divine honors, although reluctantly, because they opposed the Macedonian rule and were unwilling to worship a living person as a god. When he died, they stopped with this practice.²³

The evidence regarding the cults of Antigonos Monophthalmos and his son Demetrios Poliorketes, on the other hand, clearly proves that they had received divine honors in Athens. The reason was political: Demetrios had liberated Athens from the Macedonian King Kassandros in 307/6 BC and Demetrios of Phaleron, who had ruled Athens in Kassandros' name. To honor both father and son, Athenians created two new *phylai* (tribes) and named them *Antigonis* and *Demetrias*. Therefore, Antigonos and Demetrios were the eponymous heroes of two new tribes, plus they were worshipped as *Soteres* (*Saviors*), and Demetrios had another cult as *Kataibates* (The One Who Descends, another divine attribute) dedicated to him, which was worshipped at the site on which Demetrios dismounted from his horse when he returned to Athens in 304/3 BC to liberate the city once more from Kassandros.²⁴

That was not a lone case. During most of the 3rd century BC, Athens was under the authority of the descendants of Antigonos, called the One-eyed. His grandson Antigonos Gonatas, received divine honors from soldiers stationed in the Attic fortress of Rhamnous, and from the city of Athens. Gonatas' son Demetrios II was the last Macedonian ruler to receive such honors from the Athenian *demos*. Athenians did not abolish the cult of the Macedonian royal Antigonid family

²³ Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 47.

²⁴ *IG II³ 1 1029*, l. 12; Diod. 20.46.2; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 60, 74–76, 80; Simić, “Athens in the Hellenistic period: From Antigonos Gonatas until Sulla,” 101; John M. Camp, *The Archeology of Athens* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2004), 166.

when they gained their independence in 229 BC, but they did so at the beginning of the Second Macedonian War (200 BC) when Philip V devastated Attica.²⁵

In the peaceful period of 229–200 BC, Athenians introduced two new person-centered cults. The first was in honor of Diogenes, the last foreign commander of Piraeus. He led out his troops out of Piraeus peacefully and gave the port to Athenians. For that, he received Athenian citizenship as well as a festival organized in his name called *Diogeneia*.²⁶ In 224 BC Athens found her foreign protector in the Egyptian king Ptolemy III Euergetes (246–221 BC). Like Antigonos and Demetrios some eighty years earlier, the Egyptian king received honors in the form of a tribe (*Ptolemais*), cult with a priest, and a festival called *Ptolemaia* were established in his name. His wife and queen Berenike was honored by having one deme in the tribe *Ptolemais* named after her. The Ptolemaic festival soon became one of the most important ones in Athens, on par with *Panathenaia*, City Dionysia and Eleusinian mysteries.²⁷

Wartime brought the need for new protectors and patrons. One of the main Athenian allies in the Second Macedonian War was Attalos I, the king of Pergamon. To thank him for his aid, Athenians gave him the same honors that they had given Ptolemy III, i.e. Attalos became the eponymous hero of the tribe *Attalis*, a cult with a priest and a festival was founded in his name. His

²⁵ The cult of Antigonos Gonatas related to the festival of Nemesis: *I Rhamnous* 7, 17; prayers for the royal family: *IG II*³ 1 983, ll. 11–12; *IG II*³ 1 1002, ll. 24–25; *IG II*³ 1 1026, ll. 9–10; Liv. 31.44; Christian Habicht, “Divine Honors for King Antigonos Gonatas in Athens” in *Hellenistic Monarchies – Selected Papers*, ed. Christian Habicht (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press 2006), 286–288; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 151, 165, 167; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 144, 170–171; Homer A. Thompson, “Athens faces Adversity,” *Hesperia: The Journal of the American School of Classical Studies at Athens* 50 no. 4 (1981): 352–354; Camp, *The Archeology of Athens*, 168, 170.

²⁶ *IG II*² 1011, ll. 14–15; *IG II*² 3474, 5080; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 160–161; Simić, “Athens in the Hellenistic period: From Antigonos Gonatas until Sulla,” 102.

²⁷ Paus. 1.5, 17; *euergetes* were proclaimed on Ptolemaia: *IG II*³ 1 1313, l. 40; the priest of Ptolemy and Berenike: *IG II*² 4676; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 178, 182, 221; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 165; Allan C. Johnson, “The Creation of the Tribe Ptolemais at Athens” *The American Journal of Philology* 34 no. 4 (1913): 382, 383, 398; Kendrick Pritchett, “The Tribe Ptolemais,” *The American Journal of Philology* 63 no. 4 (1942): 423–431; Camp, *The Archeology of Athens*, 168.

son and heir Eumenes II, known as a great benefactor of Athens, had a festival named after him (*Eumeneia*).²⁸

Although the Athenians worshipped the goddess Roma, almost no Roman received divine honors. The most notable exception is Lucius Cornelius Sulla. He ravaged Athens in 86 BC and as a means of appeasing him, Athenians created a festival (*Sylleia*) and raised a statue in his honor.²⁹

New Temples

This new religious sentiment that was brought about can also be seen in sacral architecture, or to put it simply: new cults demanded new temples. Although Athenians witnessed both the construction and destruction of their temples and shrines, I will focus here on that which were built, not on those which were destroyed.

Athenaeus, quoting the attidographer Phylarkhos, says that the Athenians living on the island of Lemnos erected a temple in honor of Seluekos I and his son Antiokhos when they returned the island to the Athenians.³⁰

Eurykleides and Mikion, the liberators of Athens in 229 BC, erected the temple to *Demos* and *Kharitai* commemorating the liberation. Later that temple became a place where Athenians had erected the statues of their benefactors.³¹ Second century BC saw one of the most ambitious temple building projects not only in Athens but in the Mediterranean. The construction of the

²⁸ Liv. 31.15; Polyb. 16.25; Attalos' priest: *IG* II² 5080; *Eumeneia*: *IG* II² 2459; Mikalson, *Religion in Hellenistic Athens*, 172.

²⁹ Sulla's statue: *IG* II² 4103; *Sylleia*: *SEG* 20:110, l. 57, *SEG* 37:135, l. 2; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 311.

³⁰ Athen. 6.254F–255A. Attidographers were the writers of the local history of Athens.

³¹ *IG* II³ 1 1137, l. 39.

temple of Olympic Zeus was started by the tyrant Peisistratos in the sixth century BC. The building had lain unfinished for several centuries. Then the Seleucid king Antiokhos IV Epiphanes (175–164 BC), another one of Athens' great benefactors, decided to have it completed. He hired Roman architect Decimus Cossutius, but even then, the temple construction was not completed. The probable reason is the death of Antiokhos.³²

Beside those constructions on a larger scale, numerous small temples were built and repaired. Antidoros, a priest of Artemis Kalliste, erected a stone monument near his temple. The Athenian Council of 650 (*Boule*) decided in 220/19 BC to melt all dedicated silver items in the temple of Hero Doctor and to make a statue out of them. Sarapion from Heraklea, priest of Aphrodite, had plastered the pedestals that stand in the temple and men's bathhouse from his funds.³³

Foreign theophoric names

In the end, I will deal with a phenomenon in Hellenistic Athens which was associated with the new gods in the city pantheon. Theophoric, i.e. the names given in the honor of some god, are nothing new; they had existed in Athens much earlier. However, with the appearance of foreign gods in Athens, there are also personal names derived from the names of these gods. In order to stay within the bounds of this publication and the paper's topic, I will only mention two characteristic examples of the Egyptian deities.

³² *IG II*² 4099; *Gran. Lic.* 28.6; *Vitr. De Arch.* 7 intro 15, 17; *Strab.* 9.1.17; Habicht, *Athens from Alexander to Antony*, 166; Camp, *The Archeology of Athens*, 174.

³³ Cf. *IG II*² 1364; *IG II*³ 1 1154; besides, melting of silver dedications into statue is attested in *IG II*³ 1 1220; Sarapion: *GRA I* 39.

The first example is the personal name Sarapion (Σαραπίων), derived from the name of the Egyptian god Sarapis, whose cult Athenians officially introduced around 224 BC. The earliest known case of the use of this theophoric name is the case of an unnamed priest of Asclepius from around 170 BC, whose father was named “Sarapion.”³⁴ Assuming that the unnamed priest was then in his mid-thirties or mid-forties and that his father was in his sixties or seventies, we get ~230 BC as the possible year of Sarapion's birth. Naming children after the Egyptian god Sarapis should be seen in the context of close contact between the Athenians and the royal family in Alexandria. Sarapion as a name is much more common towards the end of the 2nd century BC. One of the wealthiest and most respected Athenians from ~100 BC, the hoplite general and the *epimeletes* (manager) of Delos, was named Sarapion.³⁵

Another well-known example is the theophoric name of Ammonios (Ἀμμώνιος). There was a rich and prominent family of Ammonioi from the deme Pambotadai in Athens, which was associated with the temple of Apollo on Delos during the 2nd century BC. The oldest recorded member of this family was Ammonios (I) whose sons Ammonios (II) and Sarapion were epigraphically mentioned on Delos: Ammonios as a priest and gymnasiarch, and Sarapion as a contributor to the temples of the Egyptian deities. Ammonios (IV) is mentioned often in epigraphic finds. He was a priest of Apollo on Delos and as such appears on the famous list of prominent Athenians who gave money to organize the last *Pythais* in 98/7 BC. Also, because of his piety, he received the honors from Delphi in 102/1 BC, which he had visited before, during the Pythian

³⁴ *IG* II³ 1 1386, l. 9; Dow, “The Egyptian Cults in Athens,” 216 claims that from the second half of the second century BC there is an increasing number of theophoric names related to Sarapis.

³⁵ *IG* II² 2336, ll. 55, 136–137, 168–169, 201–210; *IG* II² 1034+1943, l. 58; there's an inscription *IRhamnous* 56 from the end of the 3rd century BC mentioning the mercenary commander in Rhamnous who was named Sarapion, but it's not certain whether he was an Athenian citizen; other examples are: *IG*: II² 1039, l. 22; *IG* II² 1944, l. 25; *IG* II² 1961, l. 45. See also *PA* 12557–12566. Searching the name Sarapion in the *Lexicon of Greek Personal Names*, Database *Attica* (http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi accessed 25.6. 2019.) gives 47 results in total.

Games. Also, the residents of the island of Tenos honored him, and from the inscription, he was the *theoros* (the holy envoy) for the Delian festivities.³⁶

Conclusion

The Hellenistic period brought many changes into religious life all around the Mediterranean. Athens was not isolated from this. Tendencies to create something new, to syncretize foreign and domestic are probably attested best in the cultic and religious sphere of life. Strong political motives were often behind these Hellenistic innovations.

In Athens, these innovations are evident in the worship of the Egyptian deities Isis and Sarapis. They were brought to Athens by Egyptian merchants, but they became very popular when the court in Alexandria became the official protector of Athens. The same tendency can later be seen with the goddess Roma.

The divine honors bestowed upon certain individuals had an almost exclusively political dimension. When the Macedonian royal houses ruled over Athens, the Athenians deified Alexander the Great, Demetrios Poliorketes or Antigonos Gonatas. When the Athenians needed protection from the Macedonians, they gave divine honors to the Ptolemaic and Attalid kings. And, when Lucius Cornelius Sulla conquered Athens, he received divine honors as well.

³⁶ Ammonios (I): *ID* 1416 B II, ll. 72, 88; *ID* 1442 A, l. 25; *ID* 1452 A, l. 40; *ID* 2589, l. 17; Ammonios (II): *ID* 1416 B II, l. 88, *ID* 2589, l. 17; Sarapion, son of Ammonios: *ID* 1442 A, l. 25; *ID* 1452 A, l. 40; Ammonios (IV): *IG* XII 5 837, *ID* 1656. *IG* II² 2336, ll. 41–42 (= *SEG* 22:218, ll. 37–38); *FD* III 1 228; beside this, Ammonios is the name of hoplite general in 103/2. BC: *SEG* 22:218, l. 7; two epebes: *IG* II² 1039, l. 23, *IG* II³ 1 1313, l. 152; the name can be found also on the inscriptions: *IG* II² 2317, ed. 48; *IG* II² 4870, 5322, 6760; searching the name Ἀμμώνιος on *Lexicon of Greek Personal Names, Database Attica* (http://clas-lgpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi accessed 25.6. 2019.) gives 52 results. Cf. also *PA* 717–726.

Economic reasons, too, lay behind the introduction of new gods and cults in Athens and Delos. Various merchants, bankers, visitors, adventurers etc., were visiting great the harbors of Piraeus and Delos and brought with them their native cults. So did the merchants from Tyre who organized themselves around the temple of their city god Melqart. In this new environment, their god was identified with his Greek counterpart Herakles and worshipped as such. The popularity of foreign gods can be seen in personal names as well. Large numbers of Sarapions and Ammonioses are clear evidence of the popularity of those Egyptian deities.

The other, very important tendency is the re-establishment of old festivals. The Athenians revived the festivals of *Theseia*, *Aianteia*, *Pythais*, and the *Panathenaia* was celebrated with greater pomp. Still, there were innovations. The cult of Zeus *Soter* and Athena *Soteira*, established at the beginning of 3rd century BC, became one of the city's most important cults. Artemis gained a new attribute, that of *Phosphoros*. The same *Panathenaia* gained more and more international character. Athenians had summoned many foreigners, especially the Hellenistic kings to take part in their festival. Then, they used this international audience of the *Panathenaia* (as well as the Eleusinian mysteries, City Dionysia and *Ptolemaia*) to proclaim their *euergetes*, as often they were foreigners, and often they were kings. This was an opportunity for the Athenians to show themselves to the Hellenistic world and to promote their city.

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